
Rabies: A Neglected Tropical Zoonotic Disease; Implementation of A One Health Approach for Urgent Control

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ABSTRACT

In an era of medical revolutions, rabies remains a neglected tropical zoonotic viral disease, particularly in developing countries in Africa and Asia. Comprehension the causative factors of zoonotic diseases, especially viral ones, is key to improving early intervention programs and reducing mortality rates; so this article reviews the essential information about this viral infection. It belongs to Rhabdoviridae family within Lyssa genus and has negative-sense, single-stranded RNA, infects central nervous system, attacking brain and leading to encephalomyelitis and a rapid onset of symptoms. It is often transmitted through saliva of infected animals, bites and scratches are common routes of infection, and dogs are primary reservoir. Once clinical symptoms appear, the infection is fatal, and there is no proven treatment. Therefore, prevention is only effective way to combat rabies. It was concluded that the One Health approach contributes to rabies control by addressing root cause at its source, focusing on dog vaccination and breaking chain of transmission, thus protecting both humans and other animals. This approach also emphasizes urgent need for collaboration among veterinarians, physicians, environmental experts, and local authorities to effectively control this infection.

KEYWORDS: Rabies, zoonotic, viral infection, reservoir, One Health.

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INTRODUCTION

Rabies is a zoonotic viral infection [1], meaning it can be transmitted from animals to humans [2,3]. It is one of the most threatening forms of viral encephalomyelitis, affecting the central nervous system in both humans and animals [4]. It is readily treatable in the early stages, but almost 100% fatal once characteristically associated neurological signs develop, posing a significant threat to human health and the lives of many wild and domestic animals. Despite the availability of effective and safe vaccines, it remains a serious public health problem, particularly in rural areas of Africa and Asia, where the incidence is disproportionately high [5]. In 1885, Pasteur created the first vaccine and saved the life of a bite victim, a nine-year-old boy named Joseph Meister, thus beginning the modern era of rabies control [6]. This infection is geographically widespread, and its incidence increases in areas with high infection rates and high populations of wild animals and livestock, especially in the absence of effective vaccination programs. The worsening outbreak is due to several factors, including a lack of awareness about disease control and prevention, weak healthcare infrastructure, and inadequate preventative programs aimed at reducing transmission of virus from animals to humans [7].

There is an urgent need to document studies in this area due to the high incidence of this virus, particularly in regions with environmental and social conditions conducive to the transmission of zoonotic viruses [8]. Undoubtedly, understanding the etiopathogenetical factors of zoonotic infection leads to an improvement in surveillance and early intervention programs and, ultimately, can result in decreased mortality rates and lower burden on health care systems [9,10].

Therefore, experts strive to pinpoint with the utmost precision the factors that determine which hosts are most vulnerable to the virus and how it invades the nervous system, inducing clinical symptoms. This will lead to the development of successful vaccines and in establishing control strategies, particularly for endemic regions. Consequently, understanding the definition and scientific rationale of rabies is crucial for guiding research and development endeavors to eradicate an infection rates and controlling a deadly disease [11].

As it continues to pose a threat to the healthcare system, early diagnosis and prompt treatment are crucial to prevent its

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progression. The situation is further complicated by the limited diagnostic methods available in the early stages and the fact that symptoms can resemble those of other diseases [12]. Organized awareness campaigns and adherence to preventative measures contribute to limiting the spread of the disease. Furthermore, integrated international and local efforts at both the prevention and treatment levels are essential to ensure the sustainable control of this serious disease, rather than allowing it to become an intractable global health challenge [13]. This review provides key information on rabies and one health approach role in prevention and controlling this infection.

Rabies is classified as a neglected tropical disease (NTD) for several reasons:

- 1- It disproportionately harms the poor: the burden of the disease falls heavily on rural areas and impoverished settlements in Asia and Africa.
- 2- Underreporting: Many deaths occur in remote villages and are not reported, leading to official statistics that underestimate the true number [14].
- 3- Underinvestment: The reality is that historically, there has been inadequate funding for rabies research and control relative to other diseases that are 100% fatal upon symptom onset.
- 4- Economic Burden: The cost of serum and vaccine after a rabies bite is unaffordable for people in developing countries [15].

ETIOLOGY

The rabies virus belongs to the Rhabdoviridae family within the Lyssavirus genus, as illustrated in Figure (1). It is an enveloped, negative-sense, single-stranded RNA virus with a unique bullet-like shape when viewed under an electron microscope [16]. It consists of five structural proteins, with the G protein on the outer envelope being particularly prominent (Figure 2). This protein is responsible for binding to host cell receptors and stimulating an immune response by generating of neutralizing antibodies [17].

Figure 1: Taxonomy of rabies virus.

Moreover it is classified as a central nervous system virus, meaning it moves along the nerves and attacks the brain, leading to severe inflammation and a rapid onset of symptoms. These symptoms can occur immediately after the virus enters the body through an animal bite or an untreated open wound [18].

Figure 2: Structure of rabies virus.

TRANSMISSION

The virus is transmitted primarily in saliva, though the routes differ.

COMMON ROUTES

- 1- Biting: This is the main form of transmission, and is transmitted from an infected animal (most commonly a dog) through its saliva to another animal or human by bite, and contaminated saliva entering introduced into a wound (Figure 3).
- 2- Deep scratches: When the infected animal's saliva-contaminated claws scratch skin [19].

UNCOMMON (RARE) ROUTES OF TRANSMISSION

- 1- Mucous membranes contaminated: Saliva from an infected animal enters the eyes, mouth, or nose, or comes into contact with a pre-existing open wound (without a bite).
- 2- Aerosol transmission: This is highly unusual, and may happen in bat-filled caves when people get close to up to hundreds of thousands of bats or possibly also if working in laboratories with virus at high concentrations[20].
- 3- Organ transplantation: A few reported cases have occurred among recipients of corneas and solid organs from a donor who died of undiagnosed rabies [21].

Figure 3: Rabies transmission cycle (dog to human)

VIRUS RESERVOIRS

A reservoir is an animal in which the virus lives, multiplies, and is transmitted. Rabies is a zoonotic disease, and its reservoirs include:

- Dogs: These are primary reservoir worldwide and are responsible for 99% of human infections (Figure 4).
- Wild animals: These vary by geographic region.
- Bats: A major reservoir in the Americas, Australia, and parts of Europe.
- Foxes, raccoons, and skunks: Common in North America and Europe.
- Mongooses and jackals: Found in Africa and Asia.
- Cats: Can be infected and transmit the disease, but they are more often victims (infected by a wild animal or dog) than long-term primary reservoirs like dogs [22,23].

Figure 4: Reservoirs of rabies virus

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Viral propagation in the body is a complex and organized spread:

- 1- **Inoculation:** The virus generally gets into the body through a bite or scratch that is dwelling with fluids of infected animal (saliva).
- 2- **Initial Replication:** The virus replicates locally in muscle cells at the site of entry.
- 3- **Retrograde Axonal Transport:** After binding to neuronal receptors (e.g., nicotinic acetylcholine receptors) at the neuromuscular junctions, the virus migrates along axons toward CNS at a speed of 12 – 100 mm/day [24].
- 4- **CNS Infection:** After entering the spinal cord and brain and then replicating to high titers, the virus causes significant dysfunction of neurons without extensive necrosis (a feature that differentiates it from other viruses). This stage appears to be associated with development of classical symptoms of the disease, like hallucinations, pain, agitation followed by convulsions and paralysis that result in coma and death within days.
- 5- **Exocentric dispersal:** The virus spreads from the brain through the nerves to the saliva glands, skin and cornea, preparing it for passage into a new host [25].

Figure 5: Pathogenesis and transmission cycle of rabies virus.

CLINICAL PRESENTATION

The disease has five separate stages in its progression (Table 1), which usually occur as follows:

A. Incubation Period

This is typically between 20 and 90 days, but could be from one week to over a year. The time frame is influenced by distance of the bite (closer to the head), viral load, and with the density of nerves at the location of infection [26].

B. Prodromal Phase

This stage, which can last from 2 to 10 days, is characterized by non-specific flu-like symptoms as fever, malaise and headaches plus an extremely important specific one is may be paresthesia (tingling, itching or pain) at the healed bite site [27].

C. Acute Neurologic Phase

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The disease is classified into two forms:

- 1- Furious rabies (encephalitic) about 80% of cases: This is associated with hyperactivity, hallucination, fear, and seizures. The hallmark sign is hydrophobia, which is pain in the larynx and pharynx during attempts to drink water, or simply passing a sight of water.
- 2- Paralytic rabies (dumb) about 20% of cases: progressive muscle weakness at the site of the bite leading to quadriplegia, frequently mistaken for Guillain-Barré syndrome [28].

D. Coma: The patient falls into a coma lasting from hours to days.

E. Death: Death usually occurs due to respiratory and cardiac failure [29].

Table 1: The progression stages of rabies.

Stage	Phase	Duration	Key Features & Symptoms
1	Incubation Period	20 to 90 days (Range: 1 week to >1 year)	Asymptomatic.
2	Prodromal Phase	2 to 10 days	-Non-specific flu-like symptoms (fever, malaise, headaches). -Specific symptom: Paresthesia (tingling, itching, or pain) at healed bite site.
3	Acute Neurologic Phase	2-7 days	Presents in one of two clinical forms: 1. Furious Rabies (80%): Hyperactivity, hallucinations, phobias, seizures, and hydrophobia (agonizing spasms of larynx/pharynx when trying to swallow or seeing water). 2. Paralytic/Dumb Rabies (20%): Ascending muscle weakness starting at bite site and progressing to quadriplegia (frequently misdiagnosed as Guillain-Barré syndrome).
4	Coma	Hours to days	The patient loses consciousness and becomes comatose.
5	Death	Final stage	Death occurs secondary to fulminant (sudden and severe) respiratory and cardiac failure.

DIAGNOSIS

Clinical diagnosis usually is based on a history of animal exposure and classic symptoms (such as hydrophobia), while laboratory diagnosis includes:

- Nuchal skin biopsy to look for viral antigen.
- Isolation of the virus from saliva.
- Examination of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and serum to look for antibodies which may be delayed in appearance [30].
- Post-mortem diagnosis: The gold standard is examination of brain tissue using direct scintillation antibody (DFA) testing to detect Negri bodies, which are characteristic cytoplasmic inclusions in infected neurons [31].

MANAGEMENT

Once clinical symptoms appear, the infection is fatal, and there is no proven cure. Care at this stage is palliative care to reduce suffering (pain relief and potent sedation).The Milwaukee protocol, which involves inducing a coma, has not been proven to be universally effective and is not currently recommended as a standard procedure[32].

PREVENTION

Prevention is the only effective solution to combat rabies and is divided into:

A. Pre-exposure prophylaxis

Include administering the vaccine to high-risk groups as veterinarians, laboratory workers, travelers to rabies-endemic areas [33].

B. Post-exposure prophylaxis

This must begin immediately after exposure to a bite from a suspected animal and includes three crucial steps:

- 1- Wound cleaning: Wash the wound immediately right away for 15 minutes with soap and water and antiseptic (povidone-iodine). This process greatly diminishes the viral load.
- 2- Passive immunization (RIG): Injecting rabies immunoglobulin into and around the wound to neutralize the virus before it enters the nerves [34].

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- 3- Active immunization (Vaccination): Administration of a series of rabies vaccine injections (on days 0, 3, 7, 14, and sometimes 28) to stimulate the immune response that will stimulate the body's immune system to produce antibodies against the virus [35].

ONE HEALTH APPROACH AND RABIES

One Health approach recognizes that human health is linked to animal and environmental health [36]. It contributes to rabies control in the following ways:

- A root cause at the source: Instead of simply treating humans after a bite costly and insufficient to eradicate the disease, the approach focuses on vaccinating dogs.
- The equation: Vaccinating 70% of dogs in a given area breaks the chain of transmission, protecting humans and other animals [37].
- Collaborative action: This requires collaboration between veterinarians to control the disease in animals [38], human physicians to educate and treat people, environmental specialists to intervene and break the chain of transmission [39], and local authorities to manage waste and control stray dogs humanely [40].

CONCLUSION

Rabies remains a neglected zoonotic disease and a major burden on rural areas and impoverished settlements in Asia and Africa. The One Health approach contributes to rabies control by addressing causes and protecting both humans and other animals. To implement this approach effectively, collaboration between veterinarians, physicians, environmental specialists, and local authorities is essential.

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